

COOLING RATE EFFECTS IN PEEK AND CARBON FIBRE-PEEK COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Results are presented which demonstrate the significant influence of cooling rate during the fabrication process upon the properties of both unreinforced PEEK and carbon fibre reinforced PEEK composites. Slow cooling of unreinforced PEEK, at rates down to 0.5°C/min, results in increased degree of crystallinity and a reduction in toughness.

Composite panels were cooled at 19°C/min, 3°C/min and 1°C/min. A marked difference in behaviour was noted between the 3°C/min. and 1°C/min. samples. Delamination resistance under both Mode I and Mode II loadings was significantly lower for the slower cooled specimens and reduced ductility was observed in ± 45° laminates.

INTRODUCTION

Early studies of thermoplastics as matrices in composite materials showed the considerable potential of these materials, but concentrated on the amorphous polymers such as the polysulphones available at the

time {1,2}. The limited resistance of these materials to commonly used solvents slowed the acceptance of thermoplastic composites, until the introduction of carbon fibre reinforced polyetheretherketone (PEEK) and polyphenylenesulfide (PPS) in the early 1980's. The prospect of rapid forming cycles and attractive mechanical properties offered by these semicrystalline matrices has stimulated renewed interest in this class of material. Indeed further work is now in hand developing higher temperature systems {3}. However, the semicrystalline nature of PEEK and PPS, which lead to their solvent resistance, has also generated some concern. In particular, the sensitivity of matrix structure to forming conditions and notably to cooling rates during fabrication, with the possibility of detrimental effects on mechanical properties, failure processes, chemical resistance and dimensional stability has been called into question.

Previous studies on carbon fibre-PEEK composites have indicated that the degree of crystallinity, as measured by X-ray diffraction, is virtually insensitive to cooling rate over the range 10 to 700°C/min {4}, completely amorphous structure is therefore quite hard to obtain unless thin sections are cooled extremely rapidly. In contrast, carbon fibre/PPS composites tend to have a predominantly amorphous structure under normal forming conditions and a heat treatment is recommended to optimise matrix crystallinity. Work published elsewhere has indicated an effect of annealing on composite fracture {5}.

In many cases it may prove difficult to achieve a cooling rate of 10°C/min, particularly if conventional pressing equipment is being used. In this work the effect of slow cooling rates on the properties of unreinforced PEEK and carbon fibre/PEEK has been studied.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Unreinforced PEEK

Samples of 380P grade of unreinforced PEEK were supplied by the manufacturer, ICI plc, as 3mm thick injection moulded circular plaques and also as fine powder for compression moulding. The injection moulded material was cooled at a rate exceeding 700°C/min. Compression moulded plaques were cooled from 400°C at rates of 15°C/min and 0.5°C/min.

Carbon Fibre Reinforced PEEK

Composite panels were assembled from preimpregnated sheets of ICI APC2 material, 0.125mm thick, pressed to stops in a hot press at a temperature of 380°C. Forced air cooling was used which yielded a cooling rate of 3°C/min over the critical temperature range of 350°C to 200°C. Some panels were cooled more slowly, at 1°C/min, by allowing the press to cool naturally. Because the maximum cooling rate of the press was 3°C/min, to obtain greater cooling rates, panels cooled at 3°C/min were clamped in the same mould used for initial fabrication, heated in an oven to 380°C, then removed and forcibly cooled using a compressed air line. This resulted in a cooling rate of 19°C/min, well inside the manufacturer's recommended cooling range, whereas the two slower rates are both outside that range {6}.

Panels were manufactured with two different ply layups. The first was a 16-ply balanced symmetric layup with a stacking sequence of (+45, -45, -45, +45)_{2s}, and the second a 24-ply unidirectional layup with a thin layer of aluminium foil placed at the midplane for part of the area to act as a starter crack.

Fibre volume fractions were subsequently measured by acid digestion technique and found to be $63 \pm 1\%$.

Characterisation of Matrix Structure

The effects of the different cooling rates on the semicrystalline nature of the PEEK were assessed by a combination of analytical techniques and microscopy. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was performed on PEEK samples at a heating rate of 10°C/min and the crystallinity level was determined from the melting endotherm using a value of 130J/g for the heat of fusion {7}. Crystallinity in the composite was measured by a wide angle X-ray scattering technique (WAXS) which has been fully described elsewhere {4}.

Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) was used to complement these measurements and to establish the glass transition temperature in both the unreinforced PEEK and in the unidirectional CF/PEEK composite. The tests were carried out in the flexure mode, at a frequency of 10Hz and a heating rate of 2°C/min, using Polymer Laboratories equipment.

Standard microscopic techniques and permanganic etching {8} were

employed to reveal the spherulitic structure in the materials.

Mechanical Testing

Failure behaviour of the matrix under tensile loading was investigated using waisted parallel gauge creep specimens milled out from the PEEK plaques. Low-strain modulus, E , was measured in tension and strain to failure under 110 MPa loading was then determined using calibrated, accurate creep-rupture rigs.

Yield stress in pure shear, τ , was measured by the Iosipescu test method { 9 } with precisely milled 90° notches in 12mm wide specimens. Cross-head speed of 0.1mm/min was used.

The matrix fracture behaviour was studied using notched 3 point bend specimens of span 40mm, width 10mm, at a loading rate of 1mm/min. Surfaces of specimens of injection moulded material, cut both parallel and perpendicular to the mould filling direction, were polished so that final thickness was identical for injection moulded and slow cooled specimens, 2.6mm. Notches were introduced using a new razor blade to depths between 2.5 and 4mm. An estimate of fracture energy was obtained by dividing the areas under load-displacement plots by fracture surface areas for 5 specimens of each material.

Interlaminar fracture testing of composites was carried out under Mode I (opening) and Mode II (shear) loading, using the double cantilever beam (DCB) and end-notch-flexure (ENF) specimens respectively. The interpretation of these tests has been described in detail elsewhere {10 - 12} . Specimen widths were 20mm. A precrack was propagated a few millimeters from the starter crack under Mode I loading in the ENF specimen, to a total initial crack length of 25mm. Total span was 100mm.

The Mode I results were determined using a compliance calibration for each specimen obtained from the observed crack length. At least 4 specimens were tested at 2mm/min for each cooling rate; due to the largely unstable propagation, values of G_{IC} at both instability and arrest are presented, determined using crack length values measured from fracture surfaces.

Mode II values are calculated using maximum load in a shear corrected beam theory expression { 12 }, each value again representing the mean of at least 4 tests, at 0.5mm/min.

Tensile strength and failure strain of the $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates were determined on coupons 12.7mm X 127mm. The strain was measured with an extensometer; only the samples which failed within the gauge length were considered.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fracture of identical specimens of unreinforced PEEK cooled at different rates produced two distinct types of behaviour, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Load-displacement plots and fracture surfaces of (a) 0.5°C/min and (b) injection moulded unreinforced PEEK. Crack direction arrowed.

Fracture surfaces clearly show ductile plane stress deformation for the injection moulded material in contrast to the relatively brittle behaviour of the slower cooled PEEK. Table 1 summarises mechanical properties for the three cooling rates studied.

TABLE 1
Properties of Unreinforced PEEK

Material	DSC crystallinity (%)	E (GPa)	Tensile failure strain (%)	τ (MPa)	Work to Fracture (kJ/m ²)
Injection moulded	30 \pm 2	3.85 \pm 0.05	8 \pm 1	74 \pm 4	43 \pm 3
15°C/min	36 \pm 2	4.10 \pm 0.05	-	79 \pm 3	-
0.5°C/min	40 \pm 2	4.35 \pm 0.05	4 \pm 1	87 \pm 5	8.8 \pm 1.4

It may be seen that the higher degrees of crystallinity correspond to slow cooling rates and that this increase in crystallinity is accompanied by an increase in tensile modulus, increase in shear yield stress and a reduction in tensile elongation to failure. Other work on different grades of unreinforced PEEK has also indicated effects due to the degree of crystallinity on mechanical properties { 13, 14}.

The DMTA traces shown in Figure 2 (a) are in qualitative agreement with the DSC crystallinity values. The area under the $\tan \delta$ peak is related to the proportion of amorphous material present and is seen to be similar for the 15°C/min and 0.5°C/min cooled samples, both significantly different from the injection moulded sample.

Whilst it must be remembered that the 380P grade of unreinforced PEEK is not identical to the matrix material in the composite, Figure 2(b) nevertheless shows a very similar trend in the effect of the cooling rate on the $\tan \delta$ values in transverse unidirectional composite. This reflects the crystallinity values in the composite, shown in Table 2.

Figure 2. The effect of cooling rate on the $\tan \delta$ values (a) in unreinforced PEEK and (b) in the composite.

TABLE 2
Properties of CF/PEEK composites

Cooling rate	WAXS crystallinity (%)	Tensile strain to failure in +45° samples (%)	T _g DMTA (°C)
19°C/min	24±1	10.5	160±2
3°C/min	26±1	8	160±2
1°C/min	32±1	2.5	152±2

Strain to failure in +45° composite is seen to decrease markedly between the 3°C/min and 1°C/min cooled specimens. Stress-strain curves and representative fracture surfaces shown in Figure 3 underline this observation.

Figure 3. Stress-strain curves for +45° composite samples tested in tension and fracture surfaces of (a) 19°C/min and (b) 1°C/min samples.

The range of cooling rates recommended by the manufacturer extends from 700°C/min down to 10°C/min. From the results presented above it would appear that this range may extend to 3°C/min without serious detrimental effects to composite properties. The effect of even slower cooling rate is most clearly revealed in matrix dominated interlaminar fracture toughness results, shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Influence of cooling rate on interlaminar fracture of UD composite under Mode I and Mode II loading. (Error bars show maximum and minimum values obtained).

The results presented in Figure 4 clearly indicate a drop in both Mode I and Mode II delamination resistance for the slowest cooled composite. Under Mode I loading propagation in the 1°C/min cooled

material is largely unstable and the value of G_{IC} at instability indicates that with slower cooling unstable propagation occurs more readily. The small region of stable Mode I fracture in the 1°C/min cooled specimen is not noticeably different from stable propagation zones in faster cooled specimens. However, the surfaces resulting from unstable crack propagation appear more uneven in the 1°C/min cooled material.

Mode II values also drop for the slowest cooled material. The appearance of stable fracture surfaces is again found to be independent of cooling rate. The difference between the appearance of unstable fracture surfaces in 19°C/min and 1°C/min cooled samples is shown in Figure 5. Irregular undulations in the fracture surface, inbetween the fibres, are noted in the 1°C/min cooled materials. No such features have been observed in the faster cooled materials.

— 10 μ m

Figure 5. Mode II unstable propagation region in (a) 19°C/min and (b) 1°C/min specimen.

Whilst care is required in drawing conclusions from fractography alone, it may be postulated that at the slowest cooling rate there is an effect of matrix semicrystalline structure which has not been observed in previously published work on interlaminar fracture in APC2. Indeed, Crick et al. [15] have shown that for APC2, prepared within the recommended range of cooling rates, delamination passes through the

spherulites. By polishing and permanganic etching, it was established that the spherulites in both the slow cooled unreinforced PEEK and in the slow cooled composite have diameters between 5 and 15 μ m. In view of the similar dimensions of the features observed such as those in Figure 5 (b), it appears possible that the very slow cooling rate weakens the interspherulitic boundary and hence the delamination propagates around, rather than through, the spherulites.

This tentative conclusion clearly requires further substantiation but it could explain the drop off in delamination resistance for the materials cooled at very slow rates.

CONCLUSIONS

As the rate of cooling of PEEK from the melt decreases the final crystallinity level increases, both in the unreinforced 380P PEEK and in the PEEK composite. The relative magnitude of the effects is the same for both these materials.

The increase in crystallinity level has the expected effect of embrittlement of the material. Particularly marked reduction in strain to failure and in the toughness is observed at cooling rates below 3°C/min. This is considered to be due to a creation of regions of weakness between highly ordered spherulites formed during the slow cool from the melt.

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